

INFLUENCE OF DAMAGES ON THE FATIGUE LIFE OF COMPOSITE LAMINATE USING THERMAL MEASUREMENTS AND RESIDUAL STRENGTH

Kilian Demilly^{1,2,*}, Yann Marco², Vincent Le Saux²,
Guillaume Dolo¹, Emilien Billaudeau¹, Yannick Pannier³, Gurvan Moreau⁴
and Nicolas Carrère²

¹ Naval Group, Technocampus Ocean, Bouguenais, France,

² ENSTA Bretagne, UMR CNRS 6027, IRDL, Brest, France,

³ ISAE-ENSMA - UPR CNRS 3346, Institut P', Chasseneuil-du-Poitou, France,

⁴ Safran Composites, Itteville, France,

* kilian.demilly@ensta-bretagne.org

Keywords: Fatigue, Self-Heating, Initial Damages

ABSTRACT

One of the weaknesses of composite laminate is the interface between plies, as its degradation can lead to the failure of a composite structure during service. From an industrial point of view, it is to ensure that the propagation of these defects or damages could not lead to the failure of the structure between two structural inspections. This work investigates the influence of initial damages on the fatigue behavior of a carbon-epoxy composite laminate manufactured from unidirectional and 2D-woven plies. Impact tests using a drop weight device are performed and the damages mechanisms induced are observed by X-ray tomography. The impact induces delamination and matrix failures, even if no damages were visible at the contact surface. From these observations, specimens with synthetic defects are also manufactured in order to study the influence of different parameters on the damages. The effect of these initial damages on the fatigue behavior is studied by performing fatigue and self-heating tests on the as-received specimens, impacted specimens and specimens with synthetic damages obtained from a fluoropolymer film. Infrared monitoring of cyclic loading on specimen shows that these damages can be detected by the first harmonic amplitude. Moreover, the dissipation field of the specimen during the cyclic loading show that the dissipation is much higher at the location of the damage.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the weaknesses of composite laminate is the interface between plies. Indeed, the failure of this interface, called delamination, and the crack propagation that follows during service can lead to the failure of a composite structure.

These interply failures can be induced by the manufacturing process itself or by an external loading (impact for instance). From an industrial point of view, it is important to ensure that the propagation of these defects or damages could not lead to the failure of the structure between two structural inspections. This work is aimed at investigating the influence of initial damages on the fatigue behavior of the material.

The first section is devoted to presenting the experimental background. The material under investigation is presented. Then the specifications of the impact tests and the x-ray tomography observation performed are described together with the dimensions of the specimens used for those two steps. Finally, the fatigue test and self-heating protocol performed on specimens are detailed. The second section presents the results of these tests and observations on as-received and impacted specimens.

2 EXPERIMENTAL BACKGROUND

This section describes the materials, types of tests and machines used to test the material and to observe it.

2.1 Material

The material studied here is a carbon-epoxy composite laminate manufactured from unidirectional and 2D-woven plies. The stacking sequence is the following: one 2D woven ply at $\pm 45^\circ$, four UD plies at 0° and one 2D woven ply at $\pm 45^\circ$.

The specimens with synthetic defects are obtained by inserting fluoropolymer film during the manufacturing of the plate as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Manufacturing of a plate with a synthetic defect to simulate a delamination.

2.2 Impact Tests

Specimens of 150 mm x 100 mm x 3.5 mm have been impacted thanks to a drop weight device at two levels of energy: 5J and 10J. The dimensions of the specimen are set by the specifications of the impact machine.

2.3 Observations using X-Ray Tomography

Parts of various dimensions have been extracted from each impacted specimen to enable their observation through X-ray tomography. The X-Ray tomography have been performed using the RX Solution Ultratom μ CT device.

Observations have been performed with a range of resolution going from 6 to 23 μm . A resolution of 23 μm is used when the objective is to observe the full damages due to an impact or to verify the geometry of the synthetic defect implemented during the manufacturing of the plates. A smaller resolution (which may result in longer acquisition times) is employed to achieve a more detailed observation in specific zones of interest.

These observations have several goals: to reveal the microstructure of the material, to identify different types of damage caused by the impact, and to estimate the size of the damage for each energy level.

2.4 Fatigue and Self-Heating Tests on impacted specimens and specimens with synthetic defects

Once these observations have been made, the width of other impacted specimens is reduced to 40 mm to ensure the damage is inside the specimen and not going from a side of the specimen to the other side.

Therefore, 150 mm x 40 mm x 3.5 mm specimens (see Figure 2) are used to perform fatigue and self-heating tests.

Figure 2: Dimensions of impacted specimens used for quasi-static tests and fatigue tests.

The self-heating protocol consists in submitting the sample to a sequence of cyclic loading steps defined by a fixed stress ratio (R) and an increasing peak stress value (Σ^{max}). Its objective is to determine the relation between the cyclic dissipated energy and the applied stress. The evolution of the temperature is related to the dissipated energy and to the first harmonic amplitude thanks to the heat equation [1-2].

3 RESULTS

3.1 Damage mechanisms due to impact tests

For the 5J tests, no damages were visible at the contact surface. For 10J, a light print of the same dimension as the head of the impactor were visible on the top ply of the composite. In both cases, internal damages were observed.

The observations using X-ray tomography have allowed to determine the damage mechanisms inside the specimen. Two main types of damages have been observed: delamination at the interface between 2D-woven plies and unidirectional plies and matrix failures in the unidirectional plies going from a delamination to another (see the result of the 10J test on Figure 3).

Figure 3: Characteristic damages observed on impacted specimen: large delamination at the interface UD/woven (on the side opposed to the impact: bottom face), small delamination at the interface UD/woven (on the side of the impact: top face) and matrix failure (splitting) in the UD ply.

The Figure 4 shows the complete damages induced by a 5J impact.

Figure 4: Damages induced by a 5J impact.

The Table 1 estimates the size of the different damages induced by impacts. Lengths of Table 1 are the maximum length measured for each type of damage in both longitudinal direction and transversal direction.

Level of Energy [J]	Delamination Top face [mm x mm]	Delamination Bottom face [mm x mm]	Splitting [mm]
5	4.5 x 6.5	15 x 18	20
10	9 x 14	26 x 39	40

Table 1: Size of the different types of damages induced by each energy of impact.

3.2 Quasi-Static and Fatigue Results

The results of the self-heating protocol on the as-received and an impacted specimen (10 J test) are shown below.

The impact damage induces a noticeable increase of the mean dissipation on the gauge length as shown in Figure 5. The regions of interest used to calculate the mean of the dissipation is displayed as a black rectangle in Figure 6.

Figure 5: Comparison of the self-heating curves obtained on the as-received and an impacted specimen.

One of the interests of the use of an infrared camera is to obtain full field data and to observe the local thermal response of the damage. The Figure 6 shows that this damaged zone is clearly visible on the field of the rate of temperature rise.

Figure 6: Comparison of the fields of the rate of temperature rise ($^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) obtained at 1300 MPa.

The rate of temperature rise is much higher at the center of the damage compared to the side of the specimen where the values obtained seems to match the field obtained on the as-received specimen. The maximum of the rate of temperature rise obtained on the impacted specimen is twice thus obtained on the as-received specimen.

The Figure 7 shows that this damaged zone is also clearly visible on the first harmonic amplitude field.

Figure 7: Comparison of the first harmonic amplitude ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) fields obtained at 1300 MPa.

Comparisons of the results of the self-heating tests on the as-received specimens, the impacted specimens and the specimens with synthetic defects will be presented during the conference.

The S-N curves based on self-heating protocol on the as-received specimens, the impacted specimens and the specimens with synthetic defects might also be presented during the conference.

4 CONCLUSIONS

X-ray tomography shows that an impact on a carbon-epoxy composite laminate manufactured from unidirectional and 2D-woven plies induces delamination and matrix failures, even if no damages were visible at the contact surface.

Infrared monitoring under cyclic loading on as-received and impacted specimens reveal noticeable differences, especially on the two indicators evaluated (amplitude of the first harmonic and cyclic dissipation). Further analyses are required to correlate these differences to the fatigue properties.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

A part of this study belongs to the "Self-Heating" ANR - Safran - Naval Group research chair (Grant # ANR-20-CHIN-0002) involving Safran Companies, Naval Group, ENSTA Bretagne (IRDL) and Institut Pprime.

REFERENCES

- [1] L. Leveuf, Y. Marco, V. Le Saux, L. Navrátil, S. Leclercq and J. Olhagaray, Fast screening of the fatigue properties of thermoplastics reinforced with short carbon fibers based on thermal measurements, *Polymer Testing*, **68**, 2018, pp. 19-26.
- [2] L. Navrátil, N. Carrere, V. Le Saux, S. Leclercq and Y. Marco, On the ability of a viscoelastic model to predict the average cyclic energy dissipated by a 3D layer-to-layer composite, *Composite Structures*, **303**, 2023.